

Dynamic Mr Imaging of Cerebral Fat Embolism: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Cerebral fat embolism (CFE) is highly associated with long bone fractures however incidence is low. Imaging features show spectrum of findings. A 23-year-old male was admitted with right femur fracture in a road traffic accident. Surgically operated patient developed deteriorating confusion and altered sensorium. Subsequent MRI of the brain showed innumerable punctate hyperintense lesions on T2- and T2-weighted, FLAIR and restricted diffusion on DW consistent with "starfield" pattern. After 27 days hospital stay with supportive therapy patient regained complete neurological function and was discharged home. Diagnosis of CFE remains a challenge because of its various presentations, reversibility and distribution of the brain lesions. MR imaging of the brain by using T2-weighted, (FLAIR), diffusion weighted, and susceptibility-weighted imaging has been applied to CFE and has improved the ability to make an early diagnosis.

Keywords: *Cerebral Fat Embolism, Starfield pattern, MRI, long bone trauma*

INTRODUCTION

Cerebral fat embolism presents with a spectrum of signs and symptoms from altered sensorium to stupor and coma. It is part of triad of Fat Embolism Syndrome with respiratory distress and petechial hemorrhages.¹ While Fat embolism is associated with all long bone fractures, clinically evident FES is found to have incidence of only 0.9–2.2%.² This relatively uncommon condition can result in diagnostic difficulty as early CT scans of brain are usually normal.³ MRI has been shown to be more sensitive and specific and five different patterns have been described for FES, among which type 1 (starfield pattern) was observed in our case.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 23 years old male presented with fractured right femur after a road traffic accident. At presentation he was conscious. He was transferred to operation theatre for open reduction and internal fixation. Patient was shifted in ICU. Approximately 60 hours after trauma patient started developing shortness of breath along with confusion and altered sensorium with a Glasgow coma score of 10/15. CTPA was normal. Oxygen saturation was 98%. Plain CT Brain and Echocardiography were unremarkable. MRI brain revealed multiple small discrete dots like lesions of restricted diffusion on DW imaging involving centrum-semiovale, subcortical location, periventricular region, bilateral basal ganglia

and splenium of corpus callosum. (Fig1) areas corresponding to aforementioned lesions appeared hyperintense on T2WI and FLAIR sequence (Fig 2)

DISCUSSION

There are two theories to explain pathophysiology of fat embolism syndrome after long bone trauma. Mechanical theory states that fat globules have the potential to cause thrombosis by platelet aggregation and fibrin generation. These emboli can travel to pulmonary vasculature causing obstruction leading to alveolar collapse, edema and hemorrhage. Passage of these emboli to brain is responsible for neurological signs and symptoms.⁵ Presence of right to left shunt increases likelihood of systemic manifestations due to easy passage of embolus however several studies have shown presence of systemic manifestations without any presence of cardiac anomaly⁶ as it was in our case. Biochemical theory suggests that free fatty acids are generated as a result of trauma due to action of tissue lipases. High levels of free fatty acids and glycerol start a cascade of cytokine reactions which ultimately result into end organ damage. (e.g. acute respiratory distress in lungs)^{5,7} Disease process shows a variety of clinical and imaging patterns which correlate with day after trauma to long bone. There are five different patterns identified representing dynamic process of disease.⁴ Type 1; scattered cytotoxic edema (most common pattern) also known as starfield pattern. It appears as small scattered dot like lesions of variable size involving watershed zone and deep grey matter on DWI and hyperintensities on T2WI & FLAIR sequences. Type 2 is further divided into 3 subtypes; confluent cytotoxic edema, vasogenic

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Fig 1: Shows discrete areas of restricted diffusion on DW/ADC involving centrum semiovale, subcortical location, periventricular region, bilateral basal ganglia and splenium of corpus callosum.

edema and petechial hemorrhages of white matter. In type 2a (confluent cytotoxic edema) there are confluent symmetrical lesions with restricted diffusion on DWI in periventricular and sub-cortical white matter bilaterally. Lesions of vasogenic edema (type 2b) are T2W hyperintense small dots and dashes involving both grey and white matter. Type 2c lesions are more easily picked up on SWI sequence in form of multiple petechial hemorrhages which last throughout the course of disease process.

CONCLUSION

When neurologic deterioration occurs in the patient of long bone fracture then a systemic cause such as fat emboli should be considered. It is uncommon and difficult to diagnose however MRI imaging should be performed which is most sensitive in early recognition of the CFE and it helps to determine appropriate management hence improve the outcome.

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Fig 2: T2WI and FLAIR MRI images showing hyperintense discrete lesions in centrum semiovale and corpus callosum.

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